

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Fairness-Aware Graph Neural Networks for ICU Length of Stay Prediction in IoT-Enabled Environments

ANGELOS CHRISTOS MAROUDIS¹, KONSTANTINA KARATHANASOPOULOU¹,
CHARITHEA C. STYLIANIDES², GEORGE DIMITRAKOPOULOS¹, (Member, IEEE),
AND ANDREAS S. PANAYIDES², (Senior Member, IEEE)

¹Department of Informatics and Telematics, Harokopio University of Athens, 177 78 Athens, Greece

²CYENS Centre of Excellence, 1016 Nicosia, Cyprus

Corresponding author: Angelos Christos Maroudis (amaroudis@hua.gr)

This work was supported by the project Hospital Transformation through Artificial Intelligence—HOSPITAL, CODEVELOP-ICT/HEALTH, funded by the Republic of Cyprus through the Research and Innovation Foundation and the European Regional Development Fund under Grant 0322/0071.

ABSTRACT This study introduces a novel end-to-end framework designed to optimize patient outcomes and operational efficiency in intensive care units (ICUs) through fairness-aware and accurate length of stay (LOS) predictions within an IoT-enabled environment. Motivated by the concept of “fairness through unawareness,” our proposed framework employs a demographic feature exclusion strategy, preventing access to potentially discriminatory information, and thus enforcing an inductive bias that redirects learning toward non-discriminatory pattern dependencies. To address the loss of static information, we introduce a custom graph neural network that dynamically reconstructs patient relationships over time, adapting from static demographics to evolving inter-patient correlations via multi-modal embeddings (e.g., medications, procedures, vitals, conditions) and learned feature-driven edge formation. We evaluate our approach on MIMIC-IV across diverse time-series formats and demonstrate its superiority over top performing LOS prediction methods, showcasing notable performance improvements while maintaining comparable computational complexity. Additionally, we present a performance analysis highlighting our approach’s computational and predictive scalability across different graph sizes at inference, while underscoring its intrinsic ability to improve performance when deprived of demographic features by dynamically readjusting its expressive power, unlike all evaluated methodologies in this study. Finally, we present a comparative study against the literature’s top-performing LOS prediction approaches that highlights our method’s predictive superiority, demonstrating significant performance gains in predicting LOS exceeding 3 and 7 days, with improvements of up to 13.1% AUC and 10.3% ARP, and 14.1% AUC and 42.0% ARP, respectively. The code is available at https://github.com/icsa-hua/mimic_fairness_aware_gnn

INDEX TERMS Time series analysis, graph neural networks, length of ICU stay, MIMIC dataset, Internet of Things, patient outcome prediction.

I. INTRODUCTION

The healthcare industry is undergoing a significant digital transformation, with Internet-of-Things (IoT) emerging as a powerful driver of change. The IoT is revolutionizing

The associate editor coordinating the review of this manuscript and approving it for publication was Ye Liu¹.

various sectors by enabling real-time data sharing and integration across interconnected devices. This network of intelligent devices, embedded with sensors and software, is transforming how industries operate, manage resources, and deliver services [31].

In healthcare, integrating IoT and machine learning (ML) technologies poses significant challenges, especially

in intensive care units (ICUs) crucial for critically ill patients. ICUs require a multidimensional approach, utilizing diverse data inputs and specialized monitoring systems to manage patient health continuously. However, ICU care carries substantial economic burdens, influenced directly by patient stay duration and care complexity. Accurate length of stay (LOS) prediction is pivotal for optimizing ICU management, enhancing resource allocation, reducing costs, and improving patient outcomes through proactive interventions. Yet, predicting LOS in ICUs remains complex due to high-dimensional and inconsistent data, influenced by various clinical variables, while current prediction models struggle with this variability, limiting their effectiveness.

In this paper, we address the challenges of LOS prediction and introduce a fairness-aware, end-to-end IoT-enabled framework extending the preprocessing pipeline of Gupta et al. [25]. Our framework advances ICU LOS prediction by applying a combinatorial optimization framework guided by multi-objective constraints to jointly optimize predictive accuracy, fairness-aware learning, and resource-efficient management in an IoT-enabled environment. By embedding fairness constraints and architectural adaptability, it provides precise, unbiased predictions, supporting proactive patient management and optimized resource allocation. Specifically, our contributions can be summarized as follows:

- We introduce two modular extensions to the pipeline of Gupta et al. [25], focusing on (a) fairness through unawareness [54], where sensitive and discriminatory attributes are systematically excluded from model inputs, and (b) dynamic architectural adaptation, enabling model structures to account for missing information flows during both training and inference, thereby fostering more energy-efficient architectures [16].
- We propose a novel GNN topology with a dynamic graph processing strategy that improves inference-time efficiency. Unlike conventional message-passing schemes, our method restricts propagation to dynamically formed node clusters, emphasizing spatiotemporal dependencies over static correlations, and thus improving the overall computational complexity.
- Through a performance analysis study we show that our method effectively compensates for the exclusion of sensitive attributes, consistently outperforming “unfair” variants when applied to inference graphs with more than 64 patients.
- Through an extensive experimentation campaign, we offer a thorough comparison w.r.t to top-performing methods demonstrating the efficiency and effectiveness of the proposed technique in LOS prediction on the MIMIC-IV dataset.

II. RELATED WORK AND MOTIVATION

In recent years, extensive research has focused on integrating IoT, artificial intelligence (AI), and ML into healthcare, particularly within ICUs. The evolution of intensive care

began with early nursing practices and later led to the establishment of specialized units. Notably, the first ICU was created by Bjørn Ibsen in 1953 during the polio epidemic, paving the way for similar units in France, Baltimore, and Toronto [57]. Over time, ICUs have embraced IoT for continuous patient monitoring and AI for predictive analytics, enhancing real-time decision-making. Furthermore, intensive care has expanded beyond traditional ICU settings, extending to other hospital wards, emergency departments, and even prehospital care [23]. In parallel, AI-driven Clinical Decision Support Systems (CDSS) have become essential tools, processing clinical data to generate accurate, personalized diagnostic and treatment recommendations, thereby improving patient-specific care strategies [46].

A. IoT IN HEALTHCARE

The IoT has reshaped healthcare delivery by allowing continuous, real-time monitoring of patient health through interconnected devices. These systems facilitate the collection of vast quantities of patient data, including vitals and environmental conditions, which can help healthcare providers respond to critical situations promptly. In ICUs, IoT-driven solutions are particularly valuable for monitoring complex cases and providing continuous surveillance. For example, recent research has demonstrated that IoT-enabled systems improved early detection of patient deterioration by leveraging real-time data from wearable and bedside devices, resulting in more timely interventions and improved patient outcomes [52].

One major challenge with IoT in healthcare is the lack of standardized frameworks [52] for data integration across multiple devices, which can result in fragmented datasets that hinder comprehensive analyses. Moreover, IoT systems generate high volumes of data with diverse formats and structures, making it challenging to integrate these data streams into predictive models without pre-processing. Last, as IoT systems handle sensitive patient data, ensuring data privacy and security remains a critical barrier to adoption, especially in ICU settings where data breaches could have severe implications [39].

In this respect, building on the robust preprocessing pipeline of Gupta et al. [25], this study introduces an IoT-enabled predictive framework to tackle data heterogeneity and high dimensionality in ICUs. We integrate two additional preprocessing steps: (a) ‘fairness through unawareness’ [54] by denying the model access to sensitive information (Subsection IV-D) and (b) dynamically adjusting model architectures to handle missing information flows during training and inference [16] (Subsection IV-E). This ensures effective real-time IoT data integration, aiding ICU clinicians in making proactive, accurate, and fair decisions.

B. AI IN CDSS AND LOS PREDICTION

AI has become integral to CDSS, allowing for sophisticated data analysis that enhances clinical decision-making.

In ICUs, CDSS systems use ML models to provide predictive insights, aiding in diagnosis, treatment planning, and prognosis estimation. For example, Ma et al. [38] developed a CDSS that used ML to predict LOS in ICUs, demonstrating that AI-driven approaches can significantly improve ICU resource planning. However, existing CDSS models often lack adaptability to diverse patient responses, which affects the precision of their predictions in dynamic ICU environments. Moreover, many current CDSS models operate on static datasets and fail to incorporate real-time IoT data, which limits their usefulness in ICUs where timely data integration is crucial for accurate decision-making. Lastly, processing efficiency is crucial in ICU settings, yet many AI-based CDSSs face challenges with the computational complexity of high-dimensional data, leading to delays in delivering actionable insights [17].

Traditional methods for predicting ICU LOS primarily utilized statistical models such as logistic regression (LR) [44], and generalized linear models (GLMs) [48] to predict LOS based on demographic, physiological, and clinical parameters. However, these models often struggled to capture complex, nonlinear relationships in ICU data. With the increasing availability of electronic health records (EHRs), ML-based models have gained traction in LOS prediction. Several studies demonstrate different techniques such as Random Forests (RF), Gradient Boosting Machines (GBM), and XGBoost which improve predictive accuracy but have limitations in capturing complex relationships among patients, treatments, and medical conditions.

Following, we provide a thorough background on the fundamental principles and discuss the limitations of previous solutions, which we address by proposing a novel GNN architecture for healthcare challenges. Specifically, this study highlights the superior expressive power of graph-based solutions for health data [58] and their ability to adapt to patient variability by integrating real-time MIMIC-IV data within an IoT framework, providing clinicians with timely insights for accurate LOS predictions and optimized ICU resource management.

III. BACKGROUND INFORMATION

Time-series data refer to a sequence of observations ordered along the time dimension. Unlike other statistical analyses, time-series emphasizes the significance of the observation order, as successive observations are often dependent, with correlations varying based on their positions in the sequence, the nature of the problem, and the overall observation process, i.e., the observation time window and granularity [2].

In recent years, the advent of technologies for collecting, storing, and processing real-time data, driven by the rise of industrial needs and big data across fields such as energy [1], finance [40], climate modeling [42], and healthcare digitalization [10], to name a few, has led to an explosion of time-series data. This surge in production volume has driven the development of diverse solution methodologies, spanning

statistical models and neural network architectures, to address the wide-ranging challenges of time-series analysis across domains [37], [43].

The purposes of time-series analysis are diverse, including predicting future outcomes based on historical patterns, controlling and understanding the processes that generate the data, and extracting key descriptive features [2]. In this paper, however, we address the specific challenge of predicting the LOS in healthcare settings, aiming to estimate the duration of a patient's hospital stay using both historical and real-time observations.

In this context, and throughout this study, we adopt the terms 'static' and 'dynamic' with respect to the time dimension: 'dynamic' refers to variables or patterns that evolve over time, while 'static' denotes those that remain constant across the temporal axis. In the following subsections, we provide a detailed overview of time-series solution methodologies with emphasis on healthcare, while we further explore the intricacies of handling hybrid data (comprising both static and dynamic features) in Subsection IV-C.

A. THE EVOLUTION OF TIME-SERIES ANALYSIS

The concept of employing experimental observations as a tool for exploring the geometric intricacies that unfold within the abstract mathematical understanding of nonlinear systems has been well-established throughout the past decades [9]. In this regard, while the recognition that nonlinearities significantly impact the dynamics of real systems dates back more than a century (e.g., Poincaré in 1899 [45]), substantial progress in this front became feasible with advances in computational scalability, i.e., the relentless progress in shrinking semiconductor devices that has propelled advancements in computing capabilities. Specifically, the years following the revolutionary vision articulated by physicist Richard Feynman in his seminal 1959 speech, "There's Plenty of Room at the Bottom", delivered to the American Physical Society [19], marked the first era of ML.

During this period, many focused on parametric models informed by domain expertise as a means of learning temporal dynamics in a purely data-driven manner, shifting away from the purely descriptive procedures of classical time series analysis. In this way, a more structured paradigm regarding stochastic terms, based on probability theory and mathematical statistics, was introduced, leading to the modern interpretation of stochastic movements in relation to time series [32]. In the remainder of this section, we adopt the categorization framework of ML methods, divided into (a) linear and (b) non-linear models, as presented by Masini et al. [40], and provide an overview of their underlying principles.

1) LINEAR MODELS WITH PENALIZATION: EARLY INNOVATIONS IN TIME-SERIES ANALYSIS

Linear models are foundational tools in time-series analysis, as they describe the relationship between the future value of

a dependent variable and its predictors, which may include lagged values of the dependent variable as well as other explanatory factors. A penalized linear model for forecasting in time series can be expressed as:

$$y_{t+h} = \beta^\top X_t + u_t, \quad h = 1, \dots, H, \quad t = 1, \dots, T, \quad (1)$$

where y_{t+h} represents the forecast of the dependent variable h -steps ahead $X_t \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is the vector of predictors and u_t denotes the error term uncorrelated with X_t . The predictors X_t commonly include lagged values of the dependent variable (y_{t-1}, y_{t-2}, \dots), exogenous variables, or interaction terms, depending on the model specification. The parameter vector $\beta \in \mathbb{R}^n$ captures the contribution of each predictor to the forecast.

However, challenges emerge when the number of predictors exceeds the number of observations ($n \gg T$) or when predictors are highly collinear, as traditional Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) estimation becomes unreliable or infeasible due to rank deficiency [55].

To address these issues, penalized regression techniques introduce a regularization term into the loss function, stabilizing the estimation process. The penalized loss function is given by:

$$Q(\beta) = \sum_{t=1}^{T-h} (y_{t+h} - \beta^\top X_t)^2 + p(\beta), \quad (2)$$

where the first term measures the squared residuals, reflecting the model's fit, and $p(\beta)$ is a penalty term that enforces regularization on the parameter estimates. The penalty $p(\beta)$ is controlled by a tuning parameter $\lambda \geq 0$, which governs the trade-off between model complexity and predictive accuracy.

Common choices for $p(\beta)$ include the L_2 norm (Ridge regression: $p(\beta) = \lambda \|\beta\|_2^2$) and the L_1 norm (Lasso: $p(\beta) = \lambda \|\beta\|_1$), among others [33]. These regularization methods reduce overfitting, improve predictive performance, and address multicollinearity, making penalized linear models particularly effective in time-series contexts with high-dimensional predictors or limited data.

Overall, linear methods are valued for their efficiency in time-series forecasting due to low computational complexity, which in most scenarios results in fast convergence, and rapid inference. These traits make them suitable for real-time applications and datasets with many observations, provided relationships are not highly non-linear. However, their inability to fully capture complex dependencies often limits their predictive performance. Advanced techniques like penalized regression can address some of these issues but remain inadequate for non-linear patterns. This has driven the use of non-linear models, which, though computationally demanding, better capture intricate relationships and improve accuracy.

2) BEYOND LINEARITY: ADVANCING TIME-SERIES ANALYSIS WITH NON-LINEAR MODELS

As aforementioned, non-linear models were introduced to address the limitations of linear approaches in capturing complex relationships. In this framework, the forecast function f_h is assumed to belong to a general function space \mathcal{G} , and its estimation (most of the times) involves minimizing the quadratic loss:

$$S(f) = \sum_{t=1}^{T-h} (y_{t+h} - f(X_t))^2, \quad (3)$$

where $f \in \mathcal{G}$. However, when \mathcal{G} is infinite-dimensional, exhaustive optimization becomes computationally infeasible. To address this, constraints are introduced using parametric non-linear models (e.g., neural networks, regression trees) or sieve approximations [26].

The sieve method approximates \mathcal{G} with a sequence of finite-dimensional subspaces \mathcal{G}_D , where $D = 1, 2, 3, \dots$. These subspaces, or sieves, converge \mathcal{G} under a specific norm. A function $g_D(X_t)$ approximating $f_h(X_t)$ can be expressed as:

$$g_D(X_t) = \sum_{j=1}^J \beta_j g_j(X_t), \quad (4)$$

where $g_j(X_t)$ are the basis functions of \mathcal{G}_D , parameterized either fully or partially. When the basis functions, such as polynomials, are predefined (linear sieves), the estimation remains linear in β_j , enabling techniques like OLS or penalized regression.

In this context, when the basis functions $g_j(X_t)$ depend on unknown parameters (nonlinear sieves), the estimation process involves nonlinear least squares or other advanced optimization techniques. Commonly used nonlinear sieves include neural networks and regression trees, which offer the flexibility to model complex, nonlinear relationships in time-series data. These approaches, while computationally more intensive than linear models, are better suited for capturing intricate patterns and dependencies.

3) ENSEMBLE MODELS: COLLABORATIVE FRAMEWORKS FOR IMPROVED FORECASTING

During the past decade, there has been a marked trend toward more computationally demanding and complex real-world challenges. This has led, much like the transition from linear methods to non-linear frameworks, to the growing popularity of ensemble models as robust solutions, providing a solid foundation for addressing the limitations of earlier non-linear approaches. Ensemble models consist of multiple weak predictors that aggregate their individual outputs to improve performance, with the term 'ensemble' reflecting the core concept of combining multiple inducers to make a decision. In this context, the success of ensemble models lies in their ability to average different hypotheses, reducing the risk of selecting an incorrect hypothesis, and, consequently,

avoiding local minima [49]. This increases their expressive capacity and improves overall predictive performance.

Overall, ensemble methodologies fall under the umbrella of non-linear models, and are primarily divided into two categories, i.e., bagging and boosting. Bagging methods, e.g., Random Forests (RF) [7], aim to reduce variance by employing homogeneous weak predictors that operate independently and in parallel. In contrast, boosting methods, including AdaBoost [20] and GBMs [21], focus on minimizing bias by utilizing sequential and adaptive learning among predictors.

B. TIME-SERIES IN HEALTHCARE: TRENDS, CHALLENGES, AND INSIGHTS

Amid the surge of academic interest in ML during the semiconductor revolution of the 20th century, medicine emerged as a front-runner in innovation and industrial applications, with rule-based approaches achieving early success in CDSS as early as the 1970s [51], just a decade after Feynman's speech [19]. However, their predictive superiority was soon overshadowed by their high development costs, reliance on manually crafted rules, and limited adaptability, as they struggled to capture complex interactions, integrate probabilistic reasoning, and evolve with expanding medical knowledge [34].

Drawing parallels to the evolution of time-series analysis, ML in healthcare adopted similar ideas and concepts to address emerging challenges in the field, ranging from image-based diagnosis, e.g., radiology, dermatology and pathology, to health status inference through wearable devices, clinical outcome prediction, and patient monitoring [59]. While most solutions following this first era of innovation emphasized feature-based ML and explored human-interpretable designs of probabilistic nonlinear reasoning to overcome the limitations of restricted predictive capacity in isolated scenarios [13], deep neural networks and ensemble methods soon became the new standard [59], with recurrent and convolutional architectures capturing the majority of attention.

Overall, there is a vast and diverse array of time-series solutions in healthcare. To align with this study's scope, Stylianides et al. [50] provide a recent overview of state-of-the-art (SOTA) approaches for LOS and related challenges. Notably, most works emphasize ensemble models (see Subsection III-A3), while, interestingly, in some scenarios, linear regression methods achieve SOTA performance. This can be attributed to the complexity of evaluation benchmarks, where, in cases where models are assessed on the larger and more complex MIMIC dataset [30], ensemble models and neural networks demonstrate superior performance. However, in simpler datasets with fewer patient records or reduced feature dimensionality (e.g., Hospital in Yueqing, China [27] and TraumaRegister of the German Trauma Society [35]), less complex algorithms often outperform more sophisticated methods due to their ability to converge faster and avoid overfitting, thus allowing more precise and accurate exploration of the solution space [41].

In this study, we provide a thorough comparison w.r.t to SOTA methods demonstrating the effectiveness of the proposed framework to identify more efficient solutions on the more recent and challenging MIMIC-IV evaluation benchmark [29]. A summary of all adversarial methods is presented in Subsection VI-A2. Additionally, to further substantiate our claim that “*graph neural networks exhibit superior expressive power in healthcare applications compared to previous methods*”, we evaluate all approaches across a diverse set of observation settings, varying in sampling strategies, as introduced in the following sections.

C. BEYOND EUCLIDEAN CONSTRAINTS: RETHINKING CANONICAL STRUCTURES IN NEURAL NETWORKS

As discussed previously, advances in computing infrastructures and the availability of large training datasets have enabled the successful training of deep neural networks with numerous layers and degrees of freedom, driving significant breakthroughs across various fields [36]. More specifically, the inherent Euclidean structure of the input dimensional space of images, videos, text, and tabular data, to name a few, has allowed these models to exploit statistical properties such as stationarity and compositionality via local statistics. However, over the past decade, the growing interest in extending these models to non-Euclidean geometric data, driven by the intrinsic non-canonical (graph-based) nature of numerous emerging applications, e.g., social networks, sensor networks, and neuroscience, has led many to reconsider the capabilities of more traditional neural network topologies, i.e., deep feedforward, convolutional, and recurrent (memory-oriented), in sufficiently addressing these challenges [8].

In this context, graphs, as a structural extension in ML, enable deep learning (DL) models to leverage relational information through global and local connectivity, where nodes and edges are projected into low-dimensional vectors for further classification or regression. More specifically, graph filtering refines graph-structured data by extracting salient features and suppressing irrelevant connections. For example, this process, formulated as a convolution operation in either the spatial or spectral domain, includes frequency and vertex filtering techniques, enabling efficient representation learning [3], while at the same time serving as a more robust computational framework due to weight-sharing mechanisms in graph convolutional models, which significantly reduce computational complexity compared to traditional spectral methods. This paradigm has become foundational in tasks such as forecasting, classification, imputation, and anomaly detection [28].

Besides the wide adoption of GNNs and while there have been numerous novel works in health and medicine, for instance, GNN-based frameworks have proven effective in fault diagnosis (FD) by capturing intricate dependencies within structured data [15], there is yet only a minor sample of graph-based solutions for LOS prediction and similar

challenges [50]. Notably, Rocheteau et al. [47], propose an LSTM-GNN framework that models patient relationships through a diagnosis graph, combining temporal embeddings from an LSTM with relational learning in a GNN. The authors introduce a diagnosis graph construction module that encodes patient similarities based on shared diagnoses, leveraging a k-Nearest Neighbor (k-NN) pairwise similarity scheme to establish graph connectivity; however, k-NN enforces a fixed neighborhood size, potentially overlooking weak but clinically meaningful long-range dependencies, and relies on predefined similarity metrics that may not fully capture latent patient relationships. Additionally, the static nature of k-NN limits its ability to adapt to evolving patient states over time.

In this study, we propose a **dynamic graph processing framework** (introduced in Section V) that recomputes patient relationships at each timestep, allowing the graph structure to evolve with disease progression. Instead of relying solely on diagnosis-based similarity, our method integrates multi-modal embeddings (e.g., medications, procedures, vitals, conditions) to establish graph connectivity, enabling a more comprehensive and adaptive representation of patient similarities. Furthermore, by replacing heuristic similarity functions with learned feature-driven edge formation, our approach mitigates biases from predefined metrics and improves the model's expressive capacity to capture clinically relevant but non-trivial interactions [58].

IV. METHODOLOGY

A. DATA COLLECTION AND THE MIMIC-IV DATASET

Building on the aforementioned data collection paradigm (as introduced in Section II), this study adapts the proposed solutions and evaluations to the MIMIC-IV dataset, i.e., a modern electronic health record that incorporates a decade of admissions (2008–2019). MIMIC-IV includes data from 73,181 hospital stays and 50,920 unique patients, alongside other characteristics related to their ICU admissions [29]. A complete description of the MIMIC-IV dataset along with its most recent advances is provided by Johnson et al. [30], however following we provide a short description for all ICU non-demographic related features (as demographic features can be self-explanatory; i.e., age, gender, insurance, ethnicity):

- 1) **Chart events.** Patients' routine vital signs and additional care-relevant information, e.g., ventilator settings, lab values, code status, and mental status.
- 2) **Diagnosis.** Billed ICD-9/ICD-10 diagnoses for hospital admissions.
- 3) **Procedures.** Procedures documented during patients' ICU stay (e.g., ventilation), even if performed outside the ICU (e.g., X-ray imaging).
- 4) **Output events.** Information on patient outputs, such as urine and drainage.
- 5) **Medications.** Details on continuous infusions or intermittent administrations.

In the next subsections, we present a detailed overview of our proposed approach for handling collected data and dynamically constructing LOS DL predictive models. Our approach adapted to the MIMIC-IV dataset used in all experiments conducted in this study, comprises four steps, as depicted in Fig. 1. Specifically, for steps one (1) and two (2), which are responsible for the construction of the dataset, we employ the widely used pre-processing pipeline proposed by Gupta et al. [25], extending it by including two additional steps, i.e., (3) demographic bias elimination (namely fairness) and (4) dynamic model construction. These additions facilitate the management of discriminative features and ensure structural compatibility and pairing of all constructed models.

B. DATA EXTRACTION (1) AND PREPROCESSING (2): AN OVERVIEW

1) DATA EXTRACTION (1)

At first, during data extraction, the characteristics of each cohort are extracted from MIMIC-IV. One has the ability to select which of the aforementioned (see Subsection IV-A) ICU non-demographic related features desires to include in the dataset among the available clinical data associated with each admission, which are considered (and pre-processed accordingly (2)) as time-series data, e.g., labs, vitals, and medications. Specifically, the data extracted by the pipeline can be categorized into two groups; (a) demographic data (denoted as "static" data) that contains information regarding age, gender, insurance, and ethnicity for each admission record, and (b) the aforementioned time-series data (denoted as "dynamic" data). For the purposes of this study, we have included all available time-series features in our experiments.

2) PRE-PROCESSING (2)

Preceding the data extraction stage (1), the data pre-processing stage (2) is divided into four sub-processes, namely, (2.1) clinical grouping, (2.2) feature summarizing and selection, (2.3) outlier removal, and (2.4) time-series representation. At first, during clinical grouping, the data's dimensionality is reduced while retaining essential clinical information by grouping diagnoses and medications using standardized ICD-10 codes and nonproprietary drug names mapped through National Drug Codes (NDCs). The feature summarization and selection step follows, where statistical summaries of extracted features, e.g., mean frequencies and the percentage of missing values, are provided to enable users to selectively retain or exclude medical codes based on their clinical relevance. In the outlier removal step, extreme values are identified using user-defined thresholds, with outliers being either removed or replaced with boundary values to ensure data consistency. Prior to this, unit conversions are applied to ensure that all features are measured in the same units. Finally, in the time-series representation subprocess, the data is transformed into uniform time intervals for each feature, e.g., labs, vitals, medications, and procedures. This

FIGURE 1. Length of stay predictive modeling: An overview of the proposed extended pipeline.

step involves forward-filling missing values, imputing data within the observation window, and ensuring that medication dosages and procedure data are accurately represented. The result is a continuous time series dataset that encapsulates the temporal relationships of the available clinical data, associated with each admission for each patient.

C. STATIC AND DYNAMIC DATA MODELING

In the domain of predictive modeling with medical data, a common challenge arises due to the dual nature of patient information: static demographic data (e.g., age, gender, or pre-existing conditions) and dynamic time-series data (e.g., lab results, medication dosages, and vital sign measurements). Below, we formalize the challenge and outline two prominent methodological approaches.

Static Data: Let $\mathbf{X}_s \in \mathbb{R}^n$ denote the vector of static features, where $|n|$ is the total number of static (e.g., demographic) features.

Dynamic Data: Let $\mathbf{X}_t \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times T}$ denote the matrix of time-series data, where $|m|$ is the number of dynamic features (e.g., laboratory results, vitals) and $|T|$ is the number of time steps.

For instance, given a specific time-series feature X_{t,m_j} , the temporal representation of how feature j unfolds across the time dimension can be expressed as:

$$X_{t,m_j} = [x_{t_1,m_j}, x_{t_2,m_j}, \dots, x_{t_T,m_j}]^T \in \mathbb{R}^T, \quad (5)$$

where $|X_{t,m_j}|$ denotes the cardinality of the look-back window of observations, which remains consistent across all time-series features and is defined during the pre-processing step (2).

To accommodate varying granularities and durations of the look-back window, we employ two look-back window setups in this study, where given a Δt with a fixed step size δt , they are defined as:

- 1) The look-back window of 24 hours ($\Delta t = 24h$) with hourly observations ($\delta t = 1h$), i.e., $|T| = |X_{t,m_j}| = 24$.
- 2) The look-back window of 12 hours ($\Delta t = 12h$) with hourly observations ($\delta t = 1h$), i.e., $|T| = |X_{t,m_j}| = 12$.

In this context, the sampling granularity (δt) can vary depending on different preprocessing strategies as well as the inherent characteristics of the dataset, while the goal is to form a predictive function $f(\mathbf{X}_s, \mathbf{X}_t)$ that effectively combines these two data flows to predict an outcome $y \in \mathbb{R}$ (for regression tasks) or $y \in \{0, 1\}$ (for classification tasks).

In this study, all predictive functions are designed for binary classification, where the binary outcomes correspond to predicting whether a patient will remain hospitalized in the ICU for specific time horizons. These are defined as follows:

- 1) “LOS > 3 days”: Predicting whether LOS exceeds 3 days.
- 2) “LOS > 7 days”: Predicting whether LOS exceeds 7 days.

Based on the aforementioned description, two primary approaches, i.e., **Early Fusion** and **Late Fusion**, can be considered for integrating static and time-series data within ML models.

1) EARLY FUSION

This approach integrates the static data into the time-series framework at the initial stages, creating a unified representation. Specifically, static features X_s are expanded temporally to align with the time-series format in (5), as follows,

$$\mathbf{X}_s^{nT} = [\mathbf{X}_{(1),s}, \mathbf{X}_{(2),s}, \dots, \mathbf{X}_{(T),s}]^T \in \mathbb{R}^T, \quad (6)$$

where the replication spans $|T|$ time steps and $X_{(i),s} = X_{(j),s}$ for every $i, j \in T$, as static features remain constant over time. While this is conditionally true for age, we consider it valid given the short time frames of 3 and 7 days examined in this study, during which age-related variation is negligible.

In this instance, a unified representation is derived, i.e., $\mathbf{X}_x = [\mathbf{X}_s^{nT}, \mathbf{X}_t] \in \mathbb{R}^{(n+m) \times T}$, where the static and dynamic data are concatenated or merged at each time step. Following this paradigm, Early Fusion enables a unified processing logic, i.e.,

$$f = g(\mathbf{X}_x), \quad (7)$$

where g is a unified model (e.g., a transformer or RNN) capable of jointly processing the combined representation.

2) LATE FUSION

In contrast, Late Fusion processes static and dynamic data independently through separate model components, combining their outputs at a later stage, typically before the prediction layer. More specifically, the two individual information processing flows can be expressed as:

$$\mathbf{h}_s = g_s(\mathbf{X}_s), \text{ and} \quad (8)$$

$$\mathbf{h}_t = g_t(\mathbf{X}_t), \quad (9)$$

where g_s is a static data encoder (e.g., a feed-forward neural network) and g_t is a time-series encoder (e.g., a recurrent neural network, transformer, or convolutional network).

In this case the overall predictive logic flow can be expressed as,

$$f' = g(\mathbf{h}_s, \mathbf{h}_t; \mathbf{W}_h), \quad (10)$$

where f' is a fusion layer (e.g., concatenation, weighted summation), and \mathbf{W}_h represents the parameters of the final predictive layer [22].

3) INTEGRATING EARLY AND LATE FUSION IN DATA MODELING

Building upon the challenges of modeling static and dynamic data, this study employs both fusion approaches to align with the adversarial models outlined in [25]. Specifically, these approaches are integrated into CNN and LSTM architectures, where the term ‘hybrid’ refers to the incorporation of late fusion, utilizing modality-specific pipelines to process static and dynamic data independently before integration. In contrast, ‘default’ architectures rely on early fusion, where static and dynamic data are combined into a single unified representation at the input stage, foregoing independent processing streams, as previously discussed and outlined in Fig. 1.

D. FAIRNESS (3): ELIMINATING DEMOGRAPHIC BIAS FROM STOCHASTIC REASONING

What does it mean for a machine learning model to be ‘fair’, in terms which can be operationalized? (as quoted by Reuben [6])

In ML, ‘learning’ refers to transforming data into a model that captures patterns from the training data. While some patterns reflect valuable knowledge (e.g., teenagers tend to remain hospitalized for shorter periods), others encode stereotypes (e.g., minority groups based on ethnicity tend to remain hospitalized for shorter periods) that we may want to avoid. However, learning algorithms cannot inherently distinguish between knowledge and stereotypes, as these distinctions stem from social norms and moral judgments [4].

In general, the learning process can be traced back throughout all stages of ML, i.e., during (i) the construction of the dataset, (ii) the training of the model, and (iii) after

training. Based on this categorization the current state of the literature emphasizes all three aspects of fairness, and offers a variety of Pre-, In-, and Post- processing approaches [12].

To this extent, this study questions the ability of ML algorithms to retain their predictive capacity on a ‘biased’ dataset when deprived of access to sensitive information that may have influenced the unfair decisions reflected in the labels. In other words, motivated by the philosophical question of “*How does one learn to be fair in an unfair reality?*”, we extend the functionality of the proposed pipeline to incorporate a ‘Fairness Switch’ which enables or disables access to all demographic features.

From a mathematical perspective, this intervention can be expressed as,

$$\hat{Y} = f(X; \vartheta) \quad (11)$$

where $S \not\subseteq X$, when the Fairness Switch is active.

Here, \hat{Y} represents the model’s predictions, X is the set of input features, ϑ denotes the model parameters, and S refers to the sensitive demographic attributes. Activating the Fairness Switch ensures that S is excluded from the feature set X , thereby enforcing the principle of ‘fairness through unawareness.’

Overall, achieving fairness in ML requires addressing both explicit and implicit biases in data [11]. In this study, we propose GNNs specifically for their ability to model relationships and adapt to task-specific similarities, making them a robust framework for implementing fairness mechanisms like the proposed ‘Fairness Switch.’ This approach enables GNNs to disentangle sensitive attributes while maintaining predictive performance, providing a practical path to operationalizing fairness in complex health datasets.

E. DYNAMIC MODEL CONSTRUCTION (4): AN INTERACTIVE MODEL CONSTRUCTION MODULE

Lastly, step 4 of the pipeline involves constructing predictive models based on the prior binary selection of fairness by dynamically designing the model architectures (on-the-fly).

The proposed module facilitates the management of the aforementioned intrinsic duality of information flows within the construction process of medical predictive models. Specifically, the module performs conditional checks on the placement of structural elements and ensures dimensional compatibility among them, based on predefined preferences.

V. PROPOSED SOLUTION

The following section provides a detailed analysis of the proposed solution, as outlined in Fig.2. This figure encapsulates the core algorithmic logic of the prediction model embedded in (4), previously discussed and depicted in Fig.1. For a deeper understanding of the graph-based architectural components, we refer to the studies by Jin et al. [28] and Xu et al. [58], which offer insightful discussions on GNN variants for time-series classification (as also emphasized in this study) and their expressive capacity and limitations, respectively.

FIGURE 2. Proposed solution architecture.

A. INPUT FORMULATION AND PROCESSING

Formally, let $G = (V, E)$ be a directed graph, where V denotes the set of nodes representing entities (i.e., patients), and E represents edges encoding interactions or dependencies among them. The adjacency matrix $A \in \mathbb{R}^{|V| \times |V|}$ quantifies the connectivity strength, while a feature matrix X is used denote all feature representations as introduced and discussed in Subsection IV-C.

In this context, each node $v_i \in V$ is associated with a feature vector $\mathbf{x}_i \in \mathbb{R}^d$, where d is the dimensionality of the feature space. Consequently, with respect to the set of unique patients V , the feature matrix is collectively formed by these feature representations as follows:

$$\mathbf{X} = [\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2, \dots, \mathbf{x}_{|V|}]^T \in \mathbb{R}^{|V| \times d}, \quad (12)$$

where d in this instance equals $(n + m) \times T$, as defined in Subsection IV-C1.

Additionally, each node can be mapped to an embedding space through a transformation function $\phi : \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{d'}$, where d' is the embedding dimension. The resulting node embeddings \mathbf{H} capture contextualized representations:

$$\mathbf{H} = \phi(\mathbf{X}; \Theta) \in \mathbb{R}^{|V| \times d'} \quad (13)$$

where Θ denotes the trainable parameters of the embedding function. In this study, Θ comprises learnable embedding layers that encode all dataset features (see Fig. 1-1), i.e., conditions, procedures, medications, and demographics (if not excluded), into a latent space. In this context, d' can be expressed as $(n' + m') \times T$ if only static features are selected,

and as $(n' + m') \times T$ if all features are selected, according to Eq. 6. In all architectures, we employ the latter.

In that way, our approach addresses the challenge of modeling high-dimensional discrete data (observed in many modern medical datasets) by leveraging neural networks to efficiently learn contextualized embeddings. By factorizing the joint probability distribution as a sequence of conditional probabilities, the model circumvents the curse of dimensionality while maintaining computational efficiency. In a nutshell, the learnable embedding layers encode dataset features into a structured latent space, ensuring that representations remain expressive yet scalable [5].

To further clarify, the proposed GNN-based architecture employs early fusion, where all enabled features are first passed through embedding layers in parallel, i.e., one layer per feature, before being merged together to assemble a unified processing logic, as defined in Eq.6 and outlined in 4.a of Fig. 2. Here, g represents the proposed model (see Eq.7). Similarly, all adversarial methods adopted from [25] undergo the same feature processing to ensure experimental fairness in terms of embedding transformations; however, their architectures may differ in the selection of early or late fusion, as highlighted in Subsection IV-C3.

B. DYNAMIC SPATIO-TEMPORAL GRAPH PROCESSING

Motivated by the limitations of previous studies in allocating portions of a GNN's expressive capacity to the identification of time-evolving patterns, we propose a dynamic graph processing mechanism that evolves over time. In this context,

unlike static graphs, where connections remain fixed, our approach dynamically updates edge connectivity for a given batch based on feature similarities at each time step, as outlined in Algorithm 1 and depicted in 4.b.

Algorithm 1 Dynamic Graph Processing Algorithm

Require: Feature tensor $H \in \mathbb{R}^{|V'| \times d'}$, number of neighbors k , sequence length T

Require: graph convolutional layers GCL_1 , GCL_2 (optional)

Ensure: Processed node embeddings $\{H'_t\}_{t=1}^T$

- 1: Initialize output sequence $\mathcal{O} \leftarrow []$
- 2: **for** $t = 1$ to T **do**
- 3: $H_t \leftarrow H^T$ \triangleright Extract feature matrix at time step $t \in T$
- 4: $S \leftarrow H_t H_t^\top$ \triangleright Compute similarity matrix
- 5: **for** each node i **do** \triangleright Construct dynamic edge set
- 6: $\text{Top}_k(S_{i,:})$ \triangleright Find top- k similar nodes
- 7: $E_t \leftarrow E_t \cup \{(i, j) \mid j \in \text{Top}_k(S_{i,:})\}$
- 8: **end for**
- 9: $H'_t \leftarrow \sigma(\text{GCL}_1(H_t, E_t))$ \triangleright Apply 1st GCL
- 10: **if** Using 2nd GCL **then**
- 11: $H''_t \leftarrow \sigma(\text{GCL}_2(H'_t, E_t))$ \triangleright Apply 2nd GCL
- 12: Append H''_t to \mathcal{O}
- 13: **else**
- 14: Append H'_t to \mathcal{O}
- 15: **end if**
- 16: **end for**
- 17: **return** \mathcal{O}

Formally, at each time step t (2), given a transformed (with respect to Eq. 13) feature matrix $H_t \in \mathbb{R}^{|V'| \times d'}$ (3), where $V' \subseteq V$ represents the subset of nodes (patients) in a batch and d' is the feature dimension, we construct an edge index E_t by computing pairwise similarities (4)–(8). Notably, $|V'|$ corresponds to the batch size, with $V' = V$ only when the batch size equals $|V|$. Specifically, pairwise similarities per batch and time step are computed as follows:

$$S = H_t H_t^\top \quad (14)$$

where $S \in \mathbb{R}^{|V'| \times |V'|}$ captures the similarity between nodes, and \top is used to denote the transpose operation.¹ For each node i (5), we select its top- k most similar neighbors to form dynamic edges (6)–(7):

$$E_t = \{(i, j) \mid j \in \text{Top}_k(S_{i,:})\} \quad (15)$$

where $\text{Top}_k(S_{i,:})$ returns the indices of the k most similar nodes to i . Notably, the similarity relation is not necessarily symmetric, meaning that i may consider j among its top k neighbors, while the converse may not hold. This asymmetry results in a more expressive representation of a directed graph at each time step, as discussed by the authors in [58]. The

¹We use T to refer to the time domain; however, in this case, \top is used as an alternative to denote the transpose operation. For clarity, batch notations are omitted from the analysis.

resulting adjacency structure is then used within a graph convolutional layer (GCL), allowing message passing to be dynamically conditioned on temporal feature changes (9).

Specifically, at each time step, the dynamically computed graph structure E_t not only defines node connectivity but also directly influences the propagation of information through a GCL:

$$H'_t = \sigma(\text{GCL}_1(H_t, E_t)) \quad (16)$$

where σ denotes the ReLU activation function. The message-passing operation is inherently tied to the evolving graph structure, ensuring that node representations are updated based on the most relevant and temporally adaptive interactions. An optional second graph convolutional layer can further refine the embeddings (10)–(12):

$$H''_t = \sigma(\text{GCL}_2(H'_t, E_t)) \quad (17)$$

Here, it is important to note that all model derivatives evaluated on the MIMIC-IV dataset for the purposes of this study utilize only one GCL during that process, as we empirically observed that a second layer does not improve the predictive capacity of our proposed solution, while introducing a notable increase in computational complexity.

In general, by incorporating message passing into the graph construction process, we enable a learnable framework that dynamically adapts to evolving patient relationships, capturing both structural and temporal dependencies in a more expressive manner. Additionally, by dynamically re-evaluating the k -nearest neighbors at each time step, our approach introduces a relaxation of the rigid neighborhood structure imposed by static k -NN. This adaptive formulation allows patient connectivity to evolve fluidly based on temporal feature variations, capturing transient yet clinically significant dependencies that may be overlooked by a fixed similarity metric. As a result, our proposed framework mitigates the constraints of static hyperparameters, enabling a more flexible and expressive representation of evolving patient states, and thus potentially leading to more generalizable architectures with reduced biases.

C. FEATURE MATRIX RECONSTRUCTION VIA NODE EMBEDDINGS

During the dynamic graph processing step (Alg. 1), the sequence of outputs for a given batch j with respect to each time step t_i , where $i \in T$, can be denoted as follows (4.c.ii),

$$\mathbf{O}_j = \{\mathbf{o}_j^{t_1}, \dots, \mathbf{o}_j^{t_i}, \dots, \mathbf{o}_j^{t_T}\} \in \mathbb{R}^{V' \times d''}. \quad (18)$$

Here, $\mathbf{o}_j^{t_i}$ denotes the graph-processed node embeddings of batch j at time step t_i , while \mathbf{o}_{jx} (as depicted in 4.c.i) refers to node x within batch j . More specifically, the generated embedding sequences lie in $\mathbb{R}^{V' \times d''}$ and can be fully expressed as $\mathbb{R}^{B \times T \times V' \times \omega}$, where ω denotes the latent dimension of the graph embeddings.

To facilitate sequential modeling, this representation is reshaped into $\mathbb{R}^{B \times T \times (V' \cdot \omega)}$, where the extracted node

FIGURE 3. Performance analysis of graph size based on batch size: Evaluating ARP, AUC, Fairness, and computational cost in LOS>3 days prediction with a 12h observation window and 1h sampling granularity (i.e., 12h-1h format). Higher AUC and ARP indicate better performance (top-right), while smaller circles suggest lower computational cost and potential energy footprint. Batch sizes are labeled above or below the circles, with an inner-star marking fair models and an inner-dot indicating unfair models.

embeddings at each time step are stacked to form the temporal feature matrix O' .

D. TEMPORAL PROCESSING, ATTENTION AND INFERENCE

Finally, to generate the predictions, the updated spatio-temporally refined feature matrix O' undergoes temporal processing, as shown in 4.d. Specifically, an LSTM is employed to capture temporal dependencies across time steps, as follows,

$$O'' = \text{LSTM}(O') \in \mathbb{R}^{B \times T \times (V' \cdot \omega)}. \tag{19}$$

Additionally, to highlight salient temporal features, an attention mechanism is applied, computing importance scores via a scaled dot-product operation as follows,

$$A = \text{softmax} \left(\frac{O'' O''^T}{\sqrt{V' \cdot \omega}} \right) O'', \tag{20}$$

where the softmax function normalizes attention scores along the temporal axis. Lastly, the attended representation is aggregated through mean pooling, followed by a fully connected network that refines the temporal features and projects them onto the output space.

E. LIMITATIONS AND CONSIDERATIONS

Motivated by the continuous integration of ML strategies within resource-constrained frameworks (see Section II) and the limitations of previous graph-based healthcare approaches that do not explicitly emphasize computationally aware optimizations, this section further explores the intricacies of the proposed graph processing algorithm, as introduced in Subsection V-B.

Specifically, constructing a graph G from all available entities in a dataset D is a common approach but often entails significant computational and memory overhead. A substantial portion of the time required to build KNN

graphs, for instance, is spent computing pairwise similarities, i.e., accounting for up to 90% of the total construction time as also discussed by Guerraoui et al. [24]. Additionally, large graphs can impose significant memory overhead, especially in non-optimized or general-purpose hardware, where storing them in local memory (e.g., RAM) during inference may be required, particularly in methods that do not support efficient on-the-fly computation or out-of-core processing. This poses a further challenge in resource-constrained environments, such as IoT applications, where embedded devices have limited computational capacity.

In this context, our proposed approach emphasizes that the cardinality of a node subset $|V'|$ at each time step t_i for a given batch B equals the batch size $|B|$, with $V' = V$ only when $|B| = |V|$, where V denotes the complete set of nodes (patients) in the dataset. In that way, we focus on minimizing inference-time resource demands by restricting graph computations to a subgraph $G' = (V', E')$, rather than the entire graph G , and thus improving scalability in IoT environments, while at the same time paving the way for future batch construction optimization strategies. In the contrary, we acknowledge that incorporating only a subset of nodes at each iteration may constrain the expressive capacity of a GNN model by limiting the receptive field and reducing the flow of information between nodes, i.e., this restriction can impact the model’s ability to effectively aggregate neighborhood features.

However, given the proposed spatio-temporal structure of the graph, we claim that the combination of dynamic KNN selection with the learnable parameters of GCN layers allows the model to adaptively capture and propagate the most salient temporal and relational dependencies. By dynamically refining node connectivity at each step, this approach prioritizes the selection of the most informative neighbors and the most relevant time points t_i per patient, in contrast to conventional time-series models that rely on static or fully connected structures, which may dilute critical patterns across a single predictive task.

To this extent, we present a performance analysis, as shown in Fig.3, to assess the impact of varying graph sizes on inference efficiency and predictive performance. The evaluation metrics are detailed in Subsection VI-A1. Given two converged GNN variants (i.e., one fair and one unfair) trained with a batch size of 128, where samples in each batch were selected randomly, we evaluate their performance during inference across various batch sizes, i.e., {16, 32, . . . , 512}. Specifically, each experiment (represented by a circle) corresponds to a specific batch size (randomly constructed) and model type.

1) SCALABILITY AND ADAPTABILITY

Despite both models being trained with a batch size of 128, variations in batch size do not significantly degrade performance; in some cases, they enhance either AUC, ARP, or both. Notably, 512-fair and 256-fair improve both

TABLE 1. Analytical comparison of ML and DL -based solutions on MIMIC-IV for LOS prediction. Models excluding demographics (fair models) are marked with *. Bold indicates the best performance within fair and unfair categories, while blue highlights the overall best model in each sub-task (i.e., column). Additionally, cyan denotes the best-performing model for each sub-task in the machine learning category.

Type ↓	Task →	LOS > 3 days (ICU)				LOS > 7 days (ICU)			
		AUC	ARP	AUC	ARP	AUC	ARP	AUC	ARP
	Format →	12h-1h		24h-1h		12h-1h		24h-1h	
Machine Learning	Logistic Regression	0.6841	0.5276	0.6824	0.6094	0.7064	0.2514	0.7493	0.3594
	Gradient Boosting	0.7934	0.6673	0.8086	0.7527	0.8181	0.3934	0.8426	0.4973
	XGBoost	0.7889	0.6643	0.8075	0.7466	0.8132	0.3903	0.8325	0.4636
	Random Forest	0.7822	0.6494	0.7942	0.7250	0.8192	0.4233	0.8282	0.4689
Deep Learning	LSTM (Default)	0.8239	0.7140	0.8229	0.7709	0.8863	0.5511	0.8987	0.6204
	LSTM (Default)*	0.8228	0.7048	0.8194	0.7720	0.8856	0.5529	0.8822	0.6306
	TCN (Default)	0.8191	0.7014	0.8152	0.7452	0.8623	0.4974	0.8764	0.5918
	TCN (Default)*	0.8116	0.6898	0.8103	0.7625	0.8579	0.5131	0.8630	0.5788
	LSTM (Hybrid)	0.8251	0.7213	0.8263	0.7710	0.8187	0.3683	0.8990	0.6152
	LSTM (Hybrid)*	0.7731	0.6391	0.7995	0.7430	0.7996	0.3440	0.8247	0.4408
	TCN (Hybrid)	0.8096	0.6746	0.8198	0.7526	0.8201	0.3731	0.8771	0.5745
	TCN (Hybrid)*	0.7676	0.6118	0.7882	0.7019	0.7847	0.3527	0.8189	0.4621
	GNN (Ours)	0.8338	0.7175	0.8460	0.7876	0.8995	0.5758	0.9008	0.5809
	GNN (Ours)*	0.8493	0.7250	0.8472	0.7883	0.9081	0.5662	0.9045	0.6163

metrics, while 256-unfair and 512-unfair yield higher AUC. Smaller batch sizes generally perform worse due to limited nodes, which can lead to suboptimal neighbor connections. However, even with a graph size of 64 patients, performance remains comparable to larger graphs, with the unfair model achieving higher ARP compared to 128, 256 and 512.

2) PREDICTIVE QUALITY AND FAIRNESS

We observe that the fairly trained and evaluated GNN variant consistently outperforms the unfair one for batch sizes greater than 32, i.e., +0.0026 in AUC and +0.0012 in ARP, +0.0054 in AUC and -0.0091 in ARP, +0.0107 in AUC and +0.0165 in ARP, +0.0054 in AUC and +0.0058 in ARP, for batch sizes 64, 128, 256, and 512, respectively. This indicates that removing demographic features allows the model to reallocate its expressive capacity toward capturing predictive patterns in non-demographic attributes, improving performance, particularly in larger graphs where informative connections are more likely to emerge.

Lastly, it is worth noting that even at batch size 128, the fair model outperforms the unfair variants at 256 and 512, highlighting its superiority both in computational efficiency and predictive quality. The following section presents a comparative evaluation of our GNN model against alternative models using the same predictive pipeline (as introduced in Section IV) and benchmarks it against the current top-performing solutions for LOS prediction on MIMIC.

VI. EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION

A. EXPERIMENTAL SETTINGS

1) EVALUATION METRICS

a: QUALITY METRICS

To effectively quantify the predictive quality of reported solutions, we evaluate performance using two key metrics:

AUC (Area Under the Curve), which assesses the model's ability to distinguish between classes, and ARP (Average Recall Precision), which measures the trade-off between recall and precision for a more balanced performance evaluation.

b: EFFICIENCY METRICS

Efficiency metrics, on the other hand, evaluate the model's energy footprint through measures such as Floating Point Operations (FLOPs), which estimate computational complexity by quantifying the arithmetic operations required for a forward pass. Additionally, the number of parameters reflects (params) the model's size in terms of memory usage, with parameter reduction serving as an indicator of potential improvements in energy efficiency [14], [53].

2) ADVERSARIES

Our proposed GNN model is evaluated against established ML and DL baselines, each representing distinct methodological paradigms. Traditional ML models, i.e., Logistic Regression, GB, XGBoost, and RF, leverage statistical and ensemble-based learning (Subsections III-A2, III-A3). In contrast, DL models (Subsection III-A2), including LSTMs and Temporal Convolutional Networks (TCNs) in default and hybrid topologies (Subsection IV-C3), capture temporal dependencies through recurrent and convolutional architectures.

3) CONFIGURATIONS

We implement the proposed approach on Python, version 3.10.12, and PyTorch, version 2.5.1+cu124, by extending the "Extensive Data Processing Pipeline for MIMIC-IV" [25] to maintain model's compatibility with previous versions and to ensure structural consistency during the removal

or addition of all plugable (or else customizable) network elements. All experiments are conducted on a NVIDIA GeForce RTX 3060 GPU with 12GB of GDDR6 SDRAM. For all experiments we use a batch of 128 samples both during training and testing, unless specified otherwise. Additionally, all baseline models were trained for 20 epochs, or until the validation loss stopped improving for 2 consecutive epochs, using the Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD) algorithm with a learning rate of 0.01 and a momentum of 0.9.

B. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1) ASSESSING THE PREDICTIVE CAPACITY OF TOP-PERFORMING ML AND DL VARIANTS AGAINST THE PROPOSED GNN SOLUTION

a: EXPERIMENTAL FORMAT AND RESULTS

As aforementioned, to assess the predictive capacity of the top-performing and most widely used network topologies for LOS prediction and similar challenges, we conduct an experimental campaign based on the AUC and ARP performance metrics. In this subsection, all models are replicated locally and undergo training and evaluation under identical conditions to ensure fairness in assessments. In this context, we consider the two main formulations for LOS prediction, i.e., > 3 and > 7 , as introduced in Subsection IV-C, and present a thorough comparative analysis based on different time-series specification formats.

Specifically, we structure our analysis around two key components, i.e., (a) the look-back window duration (Δt) and (b) the sampling granularity (δt). This framework allows us to highlight how different models respond to varying temporal settings, where some might benefit from shorter look-back windows or coarser sampling granularities, while others exploit longer historical dependencies or finer resolutions more effectively.

The results for each component of this analysis are presented in Table 1 (a) and Figure 4 (b), respectively. Table 1 summarizes the results for two look-back window choices, i.e., 12h and 24h, with a fixed sampling granularity of 1h for both challenges, while Figure 4 highlights the performance deviations of all models across three sampling granularities, i.e., 1h, 2h, and 3h, with a fixed look-back window of 12h for LOS > 3 . Additionally, both fair and unfair model variants, as determined by the “fairness switch” described in Subsection IV-D, are included in the analysis.

b: OUTCOMES AND DISCUSSION

Firstly, in terms of predictive performance with a fixed sampling granularity of 1h (Table 1), we observe that the fair variant (excluding demographics) of our proposed GNN topology consistently outperforms all other adversarial models (both fair and unfair variants) across most evaluated sub-tasks. The only exception is the fair variant of the default LSTM, which achieves the highest ARP score for LOS > 7 days in the 24h-1h sampling format. This aligns with the theoretical foundations of LSTMs, which

FIGURE 4. Evaluating sampling granularity and the impact of demographic features. Models excluding demographics (fair models) are denoted using dotted (---) lines.

excel at capturing long-term dependencies, particularly when benefiting from extended look-back windows (Δt) and fine sampling resolutions (δt), where the number of time steps is maximized. Interestingly, even among the unfair variants, the proposed GNN model still achieves the best performance across the majority of sub-tasks.

These findings reveal two key insights: (a) the proposed GNN topology consistently outperforms all adversarial models across most experimental settings, underscoring its ability to model complex temporal-spatial dependencies more effectively than sequence-based architectures, and (b) the fairness-aware GNN variant demonstrates the advantage of graph-based representations in dynamically recalibrating expressive power and predictive capacity. Unlike recurrent and convolutional models, which rely on sequential memory mechanisms or local receptive fields, the GNN inherently captures relational structures, enabling a more adaptive encoding of patient trajectories. This capability mitigates the absence of demographic priors by leveraging latent interdependencies within time-series signals, and thus leading to superior predictive performance, as evidenced by its top-ranking evaluation scores (bold blue) across the table.

In contrast, conventional DL architectures do not exhibit the same ability to recover the lost demographic performance. This is evident in the default LSTM and TCN variants, where unfair models outperform their fair counterparts in most sub-tasks. Specifically, unfair LSTMs show an average performance gain of 0.0045 in AUC and 0.0075 in ARP,

TABLE 2. Computational comparison of adversarial DL models using parameters (M) and FLOPs (M) (shown only for the first pair to reserve space). Fair models are marked with *.

Task →	LOS > 3 days (ICU)				LOS > 7 days (ICU)			
	Params (M)		FLOPs (M)		Params		FLOPs	
	12h-1h		24h-1h		12h-1h		24h-1h	
LSTM (Default)	14.38	4902.98	14.17	8273.58	14.38	4902.99	14.17	8273.58
LSTM (Default)*	14.36	4761.03	14.15	7989.68	14.37	4761.04	14.15	7989.67
TCN (Default)	14.39	4775.60	14.17	8131.18	14.39	4775.61	14.17	8131.18
TCN (Default)*	14.37	4633.65	14.16	7847.28	14.38	4633.66	14.16	7847.28
LSTM (Hybrid)	14.28	4742.37	14.07	7935.52	14.29	4742.37	14.07	7935.52
LSTM (Hybrid)*	14.27	4725.81	14.05	7918.96	14.27	4725.81	14.05	7918.96
TCN (Hybrid)	14.29	4614.99	14.08	7793.13	14.30	4614.99	14.08	7793.13
TCN (Hybrid)*	14.27	4598.43	14.06	7776.57	14.28	4598.44	14.06	7776.57
GNN (Ours)	14.48	4881.93	14.27	8216.90	14.48	4881.94	14.27	8216.90
GNN (Ours)*	14.36	4869.59	14.17	8204.55	14.37	4869.59	14.15	8204.55

TABLE 3. Comparative results of adversarial LOS prediction methods. The results presented in this table are directly sourced from the respective publications. An 'X' indicates that the specific value was not reported in the original work.

Task	Benchmark	Format	AUC	ARP
LOS > 3 days (ICU)				
LSTM-H [25]	MIMIC-IV (v1.0)	24h-2h	0.760	0.750
RF [56]	MIMIC-III	24h-X	0.736	0.685
RF [60]	MIMIC-IV (v1.0)	X	0.716	X
GNN (Ours)*	MIMIC-IV (v2.0)	24h-1h	0.847	0.788
LOS > 7 days (ICU)				
RF [56]	MIMIC-III	24h-X	0.764	0.195
GNN (Ours)*	MIMIC-IV (v2.0)	24h-1h	0.905	0.616

while unfair TCNs exhibit an average improvement of 0.0080 in AUC and 0.0095 in ARP. This discrepancy becomes even more pronounced in hybrid topologies, where the absence of demographic features has a greater impact due to the unified processing stream. In particular, unfair LSTM (hybrid) models achieve an average gain of 0.0050 in AUC and 0.0082 in ARP, whereas unfair TCN (hybrid) variants improve by 0.0087 in AUC and 0.0110 in ARP.

Notably, traditional ML models, including Random Forest (RF), i.e., often the top-performing approach in similar studies (as discussed in VI-B3), exhibit significant performance degradation compared to all DL solutions. Specifically, the top-performing ML variants for each sub-task showcase an average performance degradation of 0.0558 in AUC and 0.1173 in ARP compared to the fair GNN variant (*). Interestingly, our experiments identify Gradient Boosting (GB) as the best-performing ML model, contradicting prior research that has favored RF for LOS prediction (see also [50]). In this context, while RF achieves the best performance for the 12h-1h format, outperforming GB by a small margin in terms of AUC (+0.0011) and by 0.0299 in terms of ARP, GB consistently demonstrates superior performance across all other settings. Specifically, for LOS > 3 days, GB outperforms RF by 0.0070 in AUC and 0.0241 in ARP for the 12h-1h format, and by 0.0140 in AUC and 0.0330 in ARP for the 24h-1h format. Similarly, for LOS > 7 days, GB surpasses RF by 0.0145 in ARP for the 24h-1h format.

Lastly, the experimental results on sampling granularity variations (Fig. 4) further validate previous findings, as the proposed GNN consistently outperforms across all δt values. However, GNN variants exhibit a performance decline with coarser granularities, highlighting their capacity to model more complex temporal structures at finer resolutions. In contrast, certain DL models, such as CNNs, perform better at coarser granularities, likely due to their ability to capture broader temporal patterns while being less sensitive to high-frequency details.

2) COMPARING THE COMPUTATIONAL EFFICIENCY OF TOP ML AND DL VARIANTS TO THE PROPOSED GNN SOLUTION

Beyond predictive performance, evaluating computational efficiency is crucial, particularly in an IoT-enabled environment. To this end, we adopt the widely used efficiency metrics, i.e., (a) FLOPs and (b) parameters, as introduced in Subsection VI-A1. Our efficiency evaluation framework aligns with DeGraph's [18] proposed implementation, and all outcomes are presented in Table 2.

The results indicate that incorporating demographic features increases computational cost, as evidenced by the systematically lower FLOPs and parameter counts of models fair variants (*), which exclude these features. While this reduction in complexity improves efficiency, it may also lead to a loss of predictive capacity by omitting relevant contextual information, as evidenced in Table 1. Additionally, the number of time-series steps significantly influences computational demands, as shown by the increase in FLOPs when transitioning from a 12h-1h format to a 24h-1h format. This is expected, as processing longer temporal sequences inherently requires more computations, particularly for models relying on sequential data processing.

Moreover, convolutional architectures demonstrate greater computational efficiency compared to LSTMs. The table reveals that TCN models consistently have lower FLOPs than their LSTM counterparts, underscoring the efficiency of convolutional operations in capturing temporal dependencies. Unlike LSTMs, which require sequential updates, convolutions enable parallelized computations, reducing overhead

while maintaining temporal feature extraction capabilities. Despite these efficiency advantages, convolution-based models do not necessarily yield superior predictive performance across all granularities, as previously discussed.

Finally, the proposed GNN solution exhibits computational complexity comparable to that of leading DL architectures while significantly surpassing them in predictive performance. Despite sharing a similar parameter count and FLOP range with LSTMs and TCNs, the GNN consistently outperforms these models, demonstrating its ability to effectively capture complex spatiotemporal dependencies without incurring excessive computational costs. This balance between efficiency and expressivity underscores its efficacy in IoT-enabled applications.

3) COMPARISON W.R.T. BEST PERFORMING LOS PREDICTION MODELS ON MIMIC

a: EXPERIMENTAL FORMAT

For the selection of adversarial solutions in this subsection, we consider all published studies that, to the best of our knowledge, have conducted experiments using the same dataset and challenge formulation. It is important to acknowledge that preprocessing strategies, training protocols, hardware selection, and execution environments often influence reported performance in comparative studies. Nevertheless, we provide a discussion on these performance-related factors, highlighting their advantages and limitations in each study.

Specifically, the pool of adversarial methods for this analysis contains (a) Wang et al.'s [56] predictive pipeline for MIMIC-III, (b) Gupta et al.'s [25] for MIMIC-IV, and (c) Zhang, Min, and Kuo's [60] methodology for predicting prolonged ICU stay (≥ 3 days) upon second admission. Wang et al. (a) report the highest performance for an LSTM hybrid architecture (LSTM-H), following a hybrid formulation akin to that in Subsection IV-C3, while Gupta et al. (b) and Zhang et al. (c) find RF performs best for both MIMIC-III and MIMIC-IV datasets. The comparative results are presented in Table 3.

b: BENCHMARK CONSISTENCY ACROSS MIMIC-III AND MIMIC-IV

We compared reported solutions in both MIMIC-III and MIMIC-IV under the assumption that the predictive performance of models evaluated in MIMIC-III serves as an accurate indicator of their performance in the highly similar MIMIC-IV, as the two datasets share fundamental characteristics. More specifically, both originate from the same institution, capture ICU patient data, follow similar clinical documentation practices, and maintain comparable relational database structures with overlapping core tables such as CHARTEVENTS, LABEVENTS, and ICUSTAYS. On the other hand, MIMIC-IV introduces refinements, including updated coding standards (ICD-10 replacing ICD-9), a more modular schema, improved version of de-identification, and higher temporal granularity. However, these changes primarily improve data quality and organization rather than alter

the underlying clinical patterns or predictive modeling tasks, ensuring that performance trends observed in MIMIC-III remain indicative of those in MIMIC-IV.

c: OUTCOMES AND DISCUSSION

The results in Table 3 highlight substantial performance gains across all tasks and metrics. For $\text{LOS} \geq 3$ days, our model improves upon RF (a), LSTM-H (b), and RF (c) by 0.111, 0.087, and 0.131 in AUC, respectively, and by 0.103 and 0.038 in ARP over (a) and (b). For $\text{LOS} \geq 7$ days, it exceeds (a) by 0.141 in AUC and 0.421 in ARP.

In this context, it is essential to highlight the configuration differences between our approach and adversarial studies. For instance, in (a), the authors adopt a two-hour resolution for the time-series data. In this regard, finer granularity, i.e., smaller sampling intervals (δt), yields higher-resolution input data, which, while increasing complexity, improves the richness of representations and thus can improve predictive performance, under the assumption that the model has sufficient capacity and that it is utilized efficiently. This is evident in Table 1, where our experimental setup employs finer granularity than the coarser-resolution ML models in this analysis. Notably, while ML models in our study perform significantly worse than DL variants, prior studies in this analysis reported superior performance for ML compared to DL.

A similar pattern emerges in feature selection. Specifically, our methodology incorporates all available features, whereas (a) includes only diagnoses and labs/vitals, and (b) relies solely on labs/vitals. Both, however, incorporate all static demographic features, while (c) only uses age, unlike our approach. This further underscores the trade-off between model capacity and the shift from demographic-based attention to richer time-series information via "fairness through awareness," which also mitigates the need for computationally intensive post-processing methods.

Lastly, (c) presents a stricter challenge formulation, aiming to predict ICU LOS for a patient's second hospital admission using only data from their first admission, along with demographics. In this regard, we observe that despite the authors' proposed feature selection methodology, RF underperforms compared to all reported solutions, primarily due to the constrained feature space imposed by the stricter challenge formulation.

VII. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

In this work, we refine the preprocessing pipeline of Gupta et al. [25] for LOS prediction by eliminating demographic features, enforcing "fairness through unawareness." Under certain structural and topological conditions, we show that fair models improve predictive performance by reallocating expressive power from static to dynamic patterns, while our refinements ensure compatibility and indicate predictive and computational generalizability across key MIMIC-IV tasks, e.g., mortality prediction, LOS estimation, and readmission. Additionally, we propose a novel GNN topology with a dynamic graph processing strategy

that improves inference-time efficiency, compared to conventional graph-based strategies, by restricting message passing to dynamically formed node clusters and prioritizing spatiotemporal dependencies over static correlations. Experimental results confirm that fairness-enforced GNN variants consistently outperform fairness-agnostic models, including top-performing DL and ensemble baselines, across diverse batch sizes, predictive tasks and sampling granularities. Furthermore, a comparison with literature's leading LOS prediction approaches highlights the superiority of our method, demonstrating notable performance improvements in predicting stays longer than 3 and 7 days.

Furthermore, this study promotes the broader adoption of GNNs in healthcare, demonstrating their predictive superiority over conventional methods and highlighting their computational efficiency, particularly in IoT-enabled environments. Future work will focus on optimal graph construction via batch sample selection, expanding the solution space by identifying equilibria within a combinatorial landscape shaped by further assessing explainability and fairness along with their predictive and computational capacity. In this regard, although non-stochastic models are well-suited for mitigating uncertainty and bias in the performance-interpretability trade-off, their explainability diminishes as feature dimensionality increases, limiting their applicability to complex health challenges where predictive human supervision of outcomes is critical. Specifically, moving forward, our work will prioritize optimizing intelligibility-cost trade-offs, addressing the limitations of static representations in SOTA methodologies, and reinforcing the broader impact of interpretability in AI, i.e., ensuring fairness, regulatory compliance, and user trust.

CODE AVAILABILITY

The code, including their extensions for (i) demographic fairness and (ii) dynamic model construction, the proposed GNN models and reproducibility scripts, are available at https://github.com/icsa-hua/mimic_fairness_aware_gnn

REFERENCES

- [1] T. Ahmad and H. Chen, "A review on machine learning forecasting growth trends and their real-time applications in different energy systems," *Sustain. Cities Soc.*, vol. 54, Mar. 2020, Art. no. 102010.
- [2] T. W. Anderson, *The Statistical Analysis of Time Series*. Hoboken, NJ, USA: Wiley, 2011.
- [3] N. A. Asif, Y. Sarker, R. K. Chakraborty, M. J. Ryan, M. H. Ahamed, D. K. Saha, F. R. Badal, S. K. Das, M. F. Ali, S. I. Moyeen, M. R. Islam, and Z. Tasneem, "Graph neural network: A comprehensive review on non-Euclidean space," *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 60588–60606, 2021.
- [4] S. Barocas, M. Hardt, and A. Narayanan, *Fairness and Machine Learning: Limitations and Opportunities*. Cambridge, MA, USA: MIT Press, 2023.
- [5] Y. Bengio and S. Bengio, "Modeling high-dimensional discrete data with multi-layer neural networks," in *Proc. Adv. Neural Inf. Process. Syst.*, vol. 12, Nov. 1999, pp. 400–406.
- [6] R. Binns, "Fairness in machine learning: Lessons from political philosophy," in *Proc. Conf. Fairness, Accountability Transparency*, Jan. 2018, pp. 149–159.
- [7] L. Breiman, "Random forests," *Mach. Learn.*, vol. 45, pp. 5–32, Jan. 2001.
- [8] M. M. Bronstein, J. Bruna, Y. LeCun, A. Szlam, and P. Vandergheynst, "Geometric deep learning: Going beyond Euclidean data," *IEEE Signal Process. Mag.*, vol. 34, no. 4, pp. 18–42, Jul. 2017.
- [9] D. S. Broomhead and R. Jones, "Time-series analysis," *Proc. Roy. Soc. London. A. Math. Phys. Sci.*, vol. 423, no. 1864, pp. 103–121, 1989.
- [10] C. Bui, N. Pham, A. T. N. Vo, A.-M. A. Tran, A. G.-T. Nguyen, and T. Le, "Time series forecasting for healthcare diagnosis and prognostics with the focus on cardiovascular diseases," in *Proc. 6th Int. Conf. Develop. Biomed. Eng. Vietnam*. Springer, Sep. 2017, pp. 809–818.
- [11] A. Castelnovo, R. Crupi, G. Greco, D. Regoli, I. G. Penco, and A. C. Cosentini, "A clarification of the nuances in the fairness metrics landscape," *Sci. Rep.*, vol. 12, no. 1, p. 4209, Mar. 2022.
- [12] S. Caton and C. Haas, "Fairness in machine learning: A survey," *ACM Comput. Surv.*, vol. 56, no. 7, pp. 1–38, Apr. 2024.
- [13] L. Chen, J. Hoey, C. D. Nugent, D. J. Cook, and Z. Yu, "Sensor-based activity recognition," *IEEE Trans. Syst., Man, Cybern., C*, vol. 42, no. 6, pp. 790–808, Nov. 2012.
- [14] Y. Chen, T. J. Yang, J. Emer, and V. Sze, "Understanding the limitations of existing energy-efficient design approaches for deep neural networks," *Energy*, vol. 2, p. L3, Jan. 2018.
- [15] Z. Chen, J. Xu, C. Alippi, S. X. Ding, Y. Shardt, T. Peng, and C. Yang, "Graph neural network-based fault diagnosis: A review," 2021, *arXiv:2111.08185*.
- [16] A. Das, S. K. Ghosh, A. Raha, and V. Raghunathan, "Toward energy-efficient collaborative inference using multisystem approximations," *IEEE Internet Things J.*, vol. 11, no. 10, pp. 17989–18004, May 2024.
- [17] M. Davuluri, "AI-driven predictive analytics in patient outcome forecasting for critical care," *Research-Gate J.*, vol. 6, no. 6, 2020.
- [18] G. Fang, X. Ma, M. Song, M. Bi Mi, and X. Wang, "DepGraph: Towards any structural pruning," in *Proc. IEEE/CVF Conf. Comput. Vis. Pattern Recognit. (CVPR)*, Jun. 2023, pp. 16091–16101.
- [19] R. P. Feynman, "Plenty of room at the bottom," in *Proc. APS Annu. Meeting*, Boston, MA, USA, Aug. 2014, pp. 1–7.
- [20] Y. Freund and R. E. Schapire, "A decision-theoretic generalization of on-line learning and an application to boosting," in *Proc. Eur. Conf. Comput. Learn. Theory*. Springer, Jan. 1995, pp. 23–37.
- [21] J. H. Friedman, "Greedy function approximation: A gradient boosting machine," *Ann. Statist.*, vol. 29, no. 5, pp. 1189–1232, Oct. 2001.
- [22] J. Gao, P. Li, Z. Chen, and J. Zhang, "A survey on deep learning for multimodal data fusion," *Neural Comput.*, vol. 32, no. 5, pp. 829–864, May 2020.
- [23] M. Greco, P. F. Caruso, and M. Cecconi, "Artificial intelligence in the intensive care unit," in *Seminars in Respiratory and Critical Care Medicine*, vol. 42. Thieme Medical, 2021, pp. 2–9.
- [24] R. Guerraoui, A.-M. Kermarrec, O. Ruas, and F. Taïani, "Fingerprinting big data: The case of KNN graph construction," in *Proc. IEEE 35th Int. Conf. Data Eng. (ICDE)*, Apr. 2019, pp. 1738–1741.
- [25] M. Gupta, B. Gallamoza, N. Cutrona, P. Dhakal, R. Poulain, and R. Beheshti, "An extensive data processing pipeline for MIMIC-IV," in *Proc. Mach. Learn. Health*, 2022, pp. 311–325.
- [26] H. Halberstam and H. E. Richert, *Sieve Methods*. Courier Corporation, 2013.
- [27] Y. Hong, X. Wu, J. Qu, Y. Gao, H. Chen, and Z. Zhang, "Clinical characteristics of coronavirus disease 2019 and development of a prediction model for prolonged hospital length of stay," *Ann. Transl. Med.*, vol. 8, no. 7, p. 443, Apr. 2020.
- [28] M. Jin, H. Y. Koh, Q. Wen, D. Zambon, C. Alippi, G. I. Webb, I. King, and S. Pan, "A survey on graph neural networks for time series: Forecasting, classification, imputation, and anomaly detection," *IEEE Trans. Pattern Anal. Mach. Intell.*, vol. 46, no. 12, pp. 10466–10485, Dec. 2024.
- [29] A. E. W. Johnson, L. Bulgarelli, L. Shen, A. Gayles, A. Shammout, S. Horng, T. J. Pollard, S. Hao, B. Moody, B. Gow, L.-W.-H. Lehman, L. A. Celi, and R. G. Mark, "MIMIC-IV, a freely accessible electronic health record dataset," *Sci. Data*, vol. 10, no. 1, p. 1, Jan. 2023.
- [30] A. E. W. Johnson, D. J. Stone, L. A. Celi, and T. J. Pollard, "The MIMIC code repository: Enabling reproducibility in critical care research," *J. Amer. Med. Inform. Assoc.*, vol. 25, no. 1, pp. 32–39, Jan. 2018.
- [31] M. Haghi Kashani, M. Madanipour, M. Nikravan, P. Asghari, and E. Mahdipour, "A systematic review of IoT in healthcare: Applications, techniques, and trends," *J. Netw. Comput. Appl.*, vol. 192, Oct. 2021, Art. no. 103164.
- [32] G. Kirchgässner, J. Wolters, and U. Hassler, *Introduction to Modern Time Series Analysis*. Berlin, Germany: Springer, 2012.
- [33] A. B. Kock, M. Medeiros, and G. Vasconcelos, "Penalized time series regression," in *Macroeconomic Forecasting in the Era of Big Data: Theory and Practice*, 2020, pp. 193–228.

- [34] C. A. Kulikowski, "Artificial intelligence methods and systems for medical consultation," *IEEE Trans. Pattern Anal. Mach. Intell.*, vol. PAMI-2, no. 5, pp. 464–476, Sep. 1980.
- [35] R. Lefering, C. Waydhas, and T. Dgu, "Prediction of prolonged length of stay on the intensive care unit in severely injured patients—A registry-based multivariable analysis," *Frontiers Med.*, vol. 11, Jun. 2024, Art. no. 1358205.
- [36] B. Lim and S. Zohren, "Time-series forecasting with deep learning: A survey," *Phil. Trans. Roy. Soc. A*, vol. 379, no. 2194, Feb. 2021, Art. no. 20200209.
- [37] Z. Liu, Z. Zhu, J. Gao, and C. Xu, "Forecast methods for time series data: A survey," *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 91896–91912, 2021.
- [38] X. Ma, Y. Si, Z. Wang, and Y. Wang, "Length of stay prediction for ICU patients using individualized single classification algorithm," *Comput. Methods Programs Biomed.*, vol. 186, Apr. 2020, Art. no. 105224.
- [39] A. Manikandan, T. Sanjay, G. Menon, R. Aswin, P. B. Bhaskar, R. M. Govind, and O. G. Ramprasad, "Issues and challenges in security and privacy with e-healthcare: A thorough literature analysis," in *Internet of Things enabled Machine Learning for Biomedical Applications*, 2025, pp. 222–247.
- [40] R. Masini, M. C. Medeiros, and E. Mendes, "Machine learning advances for time series forecasting," *J. Econ. surveys*, vol. 37, no. 1, pp. 76–111, Jul. 2021.
- [41] N. Mohammadi Foumani, L. Miller, C. W. Tan, G. I. Webb, G. Forestier, and M. Salehi, "Deep learning for time series classification and extrinsic regression: A current survey," *ACM Comput. Surv.*, vol. 56, no. 9, pp. 1–45, Oct. 2024.
- [42] M. Mudelsee, "Trend analysis of climate time series: A review of methods," *Earth-Sci. Rev.*, vol. 190, pp. 310–322, Mar. 2019.
- [43] A. Nielsen, *Practical Time Series Analysis: Prediction With Statistics and Machine Learning*. O'Reilly Media, 2019.
- [44] I. T. Peres, S. Hamacher, F. L. Cyrino Oliveira, F. A. Bozza, and J. I. F. Salluh, "Data-driven methodology to predict the ICU length of stay: A multicentre study of 99,492 admissions in 109 Brazilian units," *Anaesthesia Crit. Care Pain Med.*, vol. 41, no. 6, Dec. 2022, Art. no. 101142.
- [45] H. Poincaré, *Les Méthodes Nouvelles De La Mécanique Céleste*, vol. 3. Gauthier-Villars et Fils, 1899.
- [46] K. J. Prabhod, "Integrating large language models for enhanced clinical decision support systems in modern healthcare," *J. Mach. Learn. Healthcare Decis. Support*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 18–62, 2023.
- [47] E. Rocheteau, C. Tong, P. Veličković, N. Lane, and P. Lió, "Predicting patient outcomes with graph representation learning," 2021, *arXiv:2101.03940*.
- [48] A. Romanova, "Predicting length of stay for COPD patients with generalized linear models and random forests," in *Advances in Computer Vision and Computational Biology: Proceedings From IPCV'20, HIMIS'20, BIOCAMP'20, and BIOENG'20*. Berlin, Germany: Springer, 2021, pp. 449–457.
- [49] O. Sagi and L. Rokach, "Ensemble learning: A survey," *WIREs Data Mining Knowl. Discovery*, vol. 8, no. 4, p. e1249, Jul. 2018.
- [50] C. Stylianides, A. Nicolaou, W. A. Sulaiman, C.-A. Alexandropoulou, I. Panagiotopoulos, K. Karathanasopoulou, G. Dimitrakopoulos, S. Kleantous, E. Politi, D. Ntalaperas, X. Papageorgiou, F. Garcia, Z. Antoniou, N. Ioannides, L. Palazis, A. Vavlitou, M. S. Pattichis, C. S. Pattichis, and A. S. Panayides, "AI advances in ICU with an emphasis on sepsis prediction: An overview," *Mach. Learn. Knowl. Extraction*, vol. 7, no. 1, p. 6, Jan. 2025.
- [51] P. Szolovits, R. S. Patil, and W. B. Schwartz, "Artificial intelligence in medical diagnosis," *Ann. Internal Med.*, vol. 108, no. 1, pp. 80–87, 1988.
- [52] H. Taherdoost, "Wearable healthcare and continuous vital sign monitoring with IoT integration," *Comput., Mater. Continua*, vol. 81, no. 1, pp. 79–104, 2024.
- [53] N. C. Thompson, K. Greenewald, K. Lee, and G. F. Manso, "The computational limits of deep learning," 2020, *arXiv:2007.05558*.
- [54] S. Verma and J. Rubin, "Fairness definitions explained," in *Proc. IEEE/ACM Int. Workshop Softw. Fairness (FairWare)*, May 2018, pp. 1–7.
- [55] M. Wagner and S. H. Hong, "Cointegrating polynomial regressions: Fully modified OLS estimation and inference," *Econ. Theory*, vol. 32, no. 5, pp. 1289–1315, Oct. 2016.
- [56] S. Wang, M. B. A. McDermott, G. Chauhan, M. Ghassemi, M. C. Hughes, and T. Naumann, "MIMIC-extract: A data extraction, preprocessing, and representation pipeline for MIMIC-III," in *Proc. ACM Conf. Health, Inference, Learn.*, Apr. 2020, pp. 222–235.
- [57] J. B. West, "The physiological challenges of the 1952 Copenhagen poliomyelitis epidemic and a renaissance in clinical respiratory physiology," *J. Appl. Physiol.*, vol. 99, no. 2, pp. 424–432, Aug. 2005.
- [58] K. Xu, W. Hu, J. Leskovec, and S. Jegelka, "How powerful are graph neural networks?" 2018, *arXiv:1810.00826*.
- [59] K. Yu, A. L. Beam, and I. S. Kohane, "Artificial intelligence in healthcare," *Nature Biomed. Eng.*, vol. 2, no. 10, pp. 719–731, Oct. 2018.
- [60] M. Zhang and T.-T. Kuo, "Early prediction of long hospital stay for intensive care units readmission patients using medication information," *Comput. Biol. Med.*, vol. 174, May 2024, Art. no. 108451.

ANGELOS CHRISTOS MAROUDIS received the B.Sc. and M.Sc. degrees (Hons.) in informatics and telematics from the Harokopio University of Athens (HUA), Greece, in 2022 and 2024, respectively. During the B.Sc. studies, he was an Intern and an ML/AI Engineer with Nokia; and a Researcher with the Department of Informatics and Telematics, HUA. During the M.Sc. studies, he was a Research Associate with the National Technical University of Athens (NTUA). He is currently a Research Associate with HUA. He has involved in several EU-funded research projects, including Charity, Collabs, and Master. His research interests include deep learning, machine learning, graph algorithms, efficient neural network design, model compression, and combinatorial optimizations.

KONSTANTINA KARATHANASOPOULOU received the bachelor's degree in informatics and telematics, in 2022, and the joint master's degree in digital health and analytics from the collaborative program offered by Harokopio University of Athens, University of Piraeus, and Ionio University. She is currently pursuing the Ph.D. degree with the Department of Informatics and Telematics, Harokopio University of Athens. She is also a Research Associate with the Harokopio University of Athens. She is managing large scale research and development projects. She was an Intern Researcher with the Department of Research and Development Funding, Infineon Technologies A.G. (IFAG), Germany, where she dived into hands-on research experience on informatics, automated driving, and electronics. Furthermore, she contributes to research and development proposals and project management. Her research interests include the design and development of acceptance models, the creation of cognitive (knowledge-based) management algorithms for vehicular communication, and risk assessment research focused on highly autonomous vehicle technologies.

CHARITHEA C. STYLIANIDES received the B.Sc. degree in mathematics from the University of Nicosia, in 2020, and the M.Sc. degree (Hons.) in applied statistical modeling and health informatics from King's College London, in 2021. From 2022 to 2023, she was a Research Engineer with the KIOS Center of Excellence. Since 2023, she has been a Research Associate with CYENS Center of Excellence, Nicosia. Her research interest includes AI applications for personalized medicine.

GEORGE DIMITRAKOPOULOS (Member, IEEE) received the degree in electrical and computer engineering from the National Technical University of Athens (NTUA), in 2002, and the Ph.D. degree from the University of Piraeus, in 2007. He has been a Professor of wireless networks and applications-intelligent transport systems with the Department of Informatics and Telematics, School of Digital Technology, Harokopio University of Athens (HUA), since

2010; and the Vice-Rector of research and innovation with HUA. He has also been a Research and Development Coordinator (external) with Infineon Technologies AG, Munich, Germany, since 2018. He has been actively involved in funded research and development programs in the field of wireless communications and information technology applications, for more than 20 years. In the past, he was the General Manager with construction company and a Research Engineer with information and communication technologies (ICT) oriented companies. He is also active in start-ups in Greece and the USA. He is the author of three books and more than 220 scientific articles in international scientific journals and conferences. He is included in the top 2% scientists list worldwide, according to Stanford

University rankings, in 2021, 2022, 2023, and 2024. His research interests include the design and development of AI-enabled algorithms for the optimization of communications networks, with an emphasis on cognitive networks and non-causal reasoning, applied on intelligent transport systems, and highly automated/autonomous driving.

ANDREAS S. PANAYIDES (Senior Member, IEEE) received the B.Sc. degree in computer systems and applications from the National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, Athens, Greece, in 2004, the M.Sc. degree in computing and Internet systems from King's College London, London, U.K., in 2005, and the Ph.D. degree in computer science from the University of Cyprus, Nicosia, Cyprus, in 2011. From 2012 to 2014,

he was a Marie Skłodowska Curie Fellow with the Communications and Signal Processing Group, Imperial College London. From 2015 to 2017, he was a Visiting Research Assistant Professor with the Image and Video Processing and Communications Laboratory, University of New Mexico, USA. He was a Senior Research Fellow with the Electronic Health Laboratory, Computer Science Department, University of Cyprus, from 2015 to 2022. Since 2022, he has been a Leader of the VIDEOMICS Group, CYENS Centre of Excellence. His research interests include adaptive video processing and delivery for real time applications, computer vision for healthcare applications, and mHealth and eHealth systems and services. He has published more than 110 peer-reviewed journal and conference papers, and book chapters, in these areas, including one patent. In 2016, he was a Co-Guest Editor of the Special Issue on mHealth-Emerging Mobile Health Systems and Services for *Healthcare Technology Letters* (IET); the Special Issue on Connected Health: Status and Trends for *Frontiers in Digital Health*, in 2020; and the Special Issue on Large-Scale Medical Image and Video Analytics for Clinical Decision Support for IEEE JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICAL AND HEALTH INFORMATICS, in 2023. He is an Associate Editor of IEEE JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICAL AND HEALTH INFORMATICS.

• • •